

An internet of things framework for real-time aquatic environment monitoring using an Arduino and sensors

Md. Monirul Islam¹, Mohammad Abul Kashem¹, Jia Uddin²

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology, Gazipur, Bangladesh

²AI and Big Data Department, Endicott College, Woosong University, Daejeon, South Korea

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ABSTRACT

Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms in natural, controlled marine and freshwater environments. The real-time monitoring of aquatic environmental parameters is very important in fish farming. Internet of things (IoT) can play a vital role in the real-time monitoring. This paper presents an IoT framework for the efficient monitoring and effective control of different aquatic environmental parameters related to the water. The proposed system is implemented as an embedded system using sensors and an Arduino. Different sensors including pH, temperature, and turbidity, ultrasonic are placed in cultivating pond water and each of them is connected to a common microcontroller board built on an Arduino Uno. The sensors read the data from the water and store it as a comma-separated values (CSV) file in an IoT cloud named ThingSpeak through the Arduino microcontroller. To validate the experiment, we collected data from 5 ponds of various sizes and environments. After experimental evaluation, it was observed among 5 ponds, only three ponds were perfect for fish farming, where these 3 ponds only satisfied the standard reference values of pH (6.5-8.5), temperature (16-24 °C), turbidity (below 10 ntu), conductivity (970-1825 μS/cm), and depth (1-4) meter. At the end of this paper, a complete hardware implementation of this proposed IoT framework for a real-time aquatic environment monitoring system is presented.

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Corresponding Author:

Jia Uddin

AI and Big Data Department, Endicott College, Woosong University

Daejeon, South Korea

Email: jia.uddin@wsu.ac.kr

1. INTRODUCTION

Fish is one of the most useful sustenance on the earth. It is stacked with huge enhancements including protein and supplement D. Fish is moreover an uncommon wellspring of omega-3 unsaturated fats, which are incredibly huge for our body and psyche. Fish has loaded down with various enhancements that a large number of individuals are deficient. This consolidates great protein, iodine, and various supplements and minerals. Oily species are often considered the most helpful. That is because of the oily fish. Salmon, trout, sardines, fish, and mackerel are higher in fat-based enhancements. This fuses supplement D, a fat-dissolvable enhancement that various people are lacking. The oily fishes furthermore gloat omega-3 unsaturated fats are vital for the ideal body, brain, and unequivocally associated with a diminished threat of various ailments [1]. Respiratory disappointments and strokes are the two most ordinary explanations behind unexpected passing on the planet [2]. Fish is seen as one of the most heart-sound sustenance that we can eat. Clearly, various colossal observational assessments show that people who eat fish regularly have a lower threat of respiratory disappointments, strokes, and passing from coronary disease [3]. The omega-3 fat

docosahexaenoic destructive (DHA) is especially huge for the cerebrum and eye progression [4]. It is often recommended that pregnant and breastfeeding women eat enough omega-3 unsaturated fats [5]. Various observational examinations show that people who eat more fish have all the more moderate movements of mental lessening [6].

For these significant factors, pisciculture or fish farming is very much important for more producing fish and human beings. Before cultivating fish, it is mandatory to know which factors affect water quality parameters including pH, turbidity, water depth level, temperature, etc. Water quality is dictated by factors like temperature, straightforwardness, turbidity, water tone, carbon dioxide, pH, alkalinity, hardness, unionized smelling salts, nitrite, nitrate, essential profitability, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and microscopic fish populace [7].

The job of these parameters cannot be disregarded for keeping a sound oceanic climate and for the creation of adequate fish food life forms in lakes for expanding fish creation [8]. Consequently, there is the need to guarantee that, these ecological components are appropriately overseen and managed for good endurance and ideal development of fish. Temperature, pH, turbidity, BOD, conductivity and dissolved oxygen (DO) among these factors of water have much important role for surviving fish species [9]. The rest of the paper is arranged as follows. A literature review is stated in section 2. In section 3, the proposed architecture is discussed. The experimental setup and detailed result analysis are presented in section 4. Finally, the paper is concluded in section 5.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section discusses a segment of actions linked to the embedded system using internet of things (IoT) for pisciculture. There are many IoT-based water inspection frameworks that have been proposed. Some of them are effectively utilized for fish homesteads and hydroponics focuses [10]. An IoT system is proposed for selecting the fish species using various sensors' values including mq7, pH, turbidity, ultrasonic, and temperature sensors [11]. The main limitation of this paper is not describing the real-time scenarios of the pond's environments. Islam *et al.* [12] proposed an IoT system for fish farming thoroughly. However, no real-time values and scenarios are generated for the fish farmers. An IoT-based water quality monitoring system is proposed for aquaculture in Mekong Delta [13]. The narrowness of this system is to cultivate one fish type called pangasius at five farms. Wireless sensor network based system is proposed for monitoring water quality and fish behavior during the feeding process [14]. It is designed for tank water only. Periyadi *et al.* [15], an IoT system is mentioned for fish farming. The restriction of this system that it is designed for only fish named guppy fish and only two sensors are used including pH and salinity sensor. Alam *et al.* [16] proposed a data-driven approach for monitoring the aquatic environment for the ocean. The limitation of the model, it creates a stochastic model for predicting the actual ocean data without using IoT devices. Ahmed *et al.* [17] discussed the parameters only of aquatic environment without any IoT devices. A remote monitoring system is proposed using the IoT in [18]. An IoT system has proposed using only two sensors for fish farming in Bangladesh [19]. It is not appropriate for detecting all quality factors of the water. In Lee *et al.* [20], temperature, pH, DO levels, and ultrasonic sensors are used for monitoring the tank water. The narrowness of this system is conducted without any real-time scenarios. A mobile app for monitoring water quality is presented in [21], where two sensors including pH and temperature are used. The limitation of the model is that it is not suitable for measuring all factors of water. Considering the limitations of the state-of-art models, in this paper, we propose an IoT framework for real-time aquatic environment monitoring using Arduino and sensors. To evaluate the proposed architecture, we have utilized five ponds of various sizes and specifications.

3. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Figure 1 presents an illustration of the suggested architecture. In the IoT framework, we used four sensors including pH sensor (model 03SEN14), temperature sensor (model DS19B20), turbidity sensor (model 3305SEN1), and ultrasonic sensor (model HC-SR04). Every sensor is connected with an Ethernet shield by a various jumper on the breadboard. Then the Ethernet shield is linked with an Arduino Uno. Using the Rest-API, a cloud server is connected with this framework.

3.1. IoT framework

In the IoT framework, we used 4 sensors for measuring real-time data of each pond water. They are pH sensor, temperature sensor, turbidity sensor, and ultrasonic sensor. In Figure 2, the hardware used in the proposed IoT framework is presented. We have employed a temperature control sensor. It has an impact on the conduct, management, development and spread of fisheries government aid. The pH is an evaluation which addresses the solution's acidity or alkalinity. It is an activity level of hydrogen ion in solution. The

number ranges from 0 to 14. It is deemed neutral when its value is 7. When above 7, the solution is alkaline, and below 7, then acidic water is considered. The pH range for fish viability in a pond is often between 6.5 and 8.5. It is the major survival element. That is why we use this sensor in our system. The ultrasonic sensor can detect the depth level of water. Every fish species cannot live on one level. Fishes live in upper level or middle level or lower level. For measuring this point, we used this sensor in our system. Turbidity is the unwanted something in the water that hinders to production of fish species. For measuring this issue, we used a turbidity sensor. In the proposed architecture, we have used an ethernet shield and Arduino Uno [22]. Arduino Uno may be simply connected to the internet with ethernet shield. This shield allows Arduino to transfer data from sensors with internet connections to a cloud server.

Figure 1. Illustration of suggested methodology

Figure 2. Utilized hardware of our system-turbidity sensor, temperature sensor, pH sensor, ultrasonic sensor, Arduino Uno, and ethernet shield

3.2. Cloud server and real-time data

The real-time data were stored in the ThingSpeak IoT server. This is a free cloud server for permitting to gather and store sensor information in the cloud and create IoT applications. It is stored in comma-separated values (CSV), extensible markup language (XML), and JavaScript object notation (JSON) format. In the experiments, we have stored the data for each pond for 4 hours 10 minutes. Among the 250 minutes' data, we have considered data after 3 minutes as we only consider the data for the stable circuit.

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULT ANALYSIS

We have considered 5 ponds for monitoring the quality of water using the proposed IoT system. In the experimental evaluation, we do programming in Arduino suite software. Due to the lack of portability of the hardware, we have collected water from the ponds using a bucket from all the ponds, which is displayed

in Figure 3. Table 1 illustrates the specifications of all ponds. The depth of the pond should not be less than 1 meter or more than 5 meters, the best depth is 2 meters. After collecting, we dipped our all sensors into the water for getting real-time data. As experimenting sample, Figure 4 shows the experiment of pH values, turbidity values, and temperature values, respectively in water for analysis of water quality.

Figure 3. Water collection from all ponds: (a) pond 1, (b) pond 2, (c) pond 3, (d) pond 4, and (e) pond 5

Table 1. Specification of all ponds

Term	Pond 1	Pond 2	Pond 3	Pond 4	Pond 5
Length(m)	26	52	105	156	40
Width(m)	17	30	35	80	20
Water depth(m)	1-2	1-2	1-2	2-4	1-3

Figure 4. Experimenting water of (a) pH, (b) turbidity, and (c) temperature value in some ponds

pH sensors for all experiments are tested on between 8:50-9:30 pm on 20 December 2020, on between 11:18-11:50 am on 21 December 2020, on between 2:00-2:50 pm on 20 December 2020, on between 6:00-6:50 pm on 20 December 2020, and on between 2:30-3:20 pm on 22 December 2020 for pond 1, pond 2, pond 3, pond 4, and pond 5, respectively. We take 4 hours 10 minutes from 3 days in all experiments. In the Arduino suite, we keep the baud rate 9600 for serial begin function for all experiments.

The experiment of the turbidity sensors of all experiments is on between 10:00-10:50 am on 23 December 2020, on between 12:00-12:50 pm on 23 December 2020, on between 2:10-3:00 pm on 23 December 2020, on between 4:00-4:50 pm on 23 December 2020, and on between 5:20-6:10 pm on 23 December 2020 for all ponds, respectively. We take 4 hours 10 minutes from 1 day in all experiments.

Temperature sensors for all experiments are tested on between 3:00-3:50 pm on 25 December 2020, on between 4:10-5:00 am on 25 December 2020, on between 10:00-10:50 am on 25 December 2020, on between 11:09-11:59 am on 25 December 2020, and on between 12:20-1:10 pm on 25 December 2020 in all ponds, respectively. We take 4 hours 10 minutes from 1 day for temperature experiment in all experiments. In the Arduino suite, we keep the baud rate 9600 for serial begin function for all experiments.

Figure 5 shows the graph of the pH value of the real-time data. The range of pH value is 6.02-8.39, 8.57-8.87, 6.00-7.83, 6.51-8.30 and 3.84-3.95 for pond 1, pond 2, pond 3, pond 4, and pond 5, respectively. The pH range of pond 1 is suited for fish production according to the standard reference value, 6.5-8.5 [23]. The received pH value, 8.57-8.87 from pond 2 is greater than the ideal value. Therefore, this pond is not perfect for fish farming. In pond 3, the range of pH is 6.00-7.83. It is almost near to ideal range, 6.5-8.5. Pond 4 also provides acceptable values of pH. The range of pH values is not perfect for fish farming for pond 5. This causes to die for fish species. It is a death point for acidity.

Figure 5. Real-time value of pH of all experiments

Figure 6 displays a graph of real-time values of turbidity from all of the experiments. The range of turbidity values is 3.55-3.57 NTU, 3.41-3.50 NTU, 3.31-3.49 NTU, 3.60-3.62 NTU, and 3.56-3.58 NTU for pond 1, pond 2, pond 3, pond 4, and pond 5, respectively. The acceptable turbidity range is below 10 NTU for fish farming [24]. Figure 6 dictates that all received values of turbidity from all experiments are acceptable. Figure 7 displays graph of real-time values of temperature from all of experiments. The range of temperature values is 17.50-17.75 °C, 17.75-18.00 °C, 20.87-21.06 °C, 21.06-21.44 °C, and 21.06-21.25 °C for pond 1, pond 2, pond 3, pond 4, and pond 5, respectively. The overall acceptable range of temperature for pond is 16-24 °C [25]. The received real-time sensor of all experiments is perfect for fish farming.

Figure 6. Real-time value of turbidity of all experiments

Conductivity is a helpful parameter to assess the virtue of water. It is subject to the ionic fixation and water temperature [26]. Temperature in a water body is directly related to its conductivity. At 25 °C, has a specific conductance of 1,413 mmhos/cm but at 20 °C and 30 °C, the values are 1,273 and 1,547 mmhos/cm, respectively [27]. When water temperature increases, conductivity increases. Conductivity readings can rise by 2-4 percent for each 1 °C increase. By raising ion mobility, the temperature impacts conductivity. The ideal range of it is 970-1825 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ [28].

Figure 8 displays graph of real-time values of conductivity from all of experiments. The range of conductivity values is 989-1003 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 1003-1017 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 1179-1190 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 1193-1215 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and 1190-1203 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for pond 1, pond 2, pond 3, pond 4, and pond 5, respectively. The received real-time sensor of all experiments is perfect for fish farming. Table 2 illustrates the summary of all received values for each pond. According to the ideal range of all parameters, pond 1, pond 3, and pond 4 are eligible for fish farming. The pond 2 is not perfect for cultivation fish. Because of the pH value, 8.57-8.87 is higher than the ideal values. It is the point of the slow growth of fish. The pond 5 is not suited for the lower pH value, 3.84-3.95. This causes fish death. That is why, we could not give suggestions for pond 1 and pond 2 to fish farmers.

Figure 7. Real-time value of temperature of all experiments

Figure 8. Real-time value of conductivity of all experiments

Table 2. Received values for suggesting pond

Pond	pH	Temperature (°C)	Turbidity (ntu)	Depth (m)	Conductivity (μS/cm)	Remarks
Pond 1	6.02-8.39	17.50-17.75	3.55-3.57	1-2	989-1003	Recommended
Pond 2	8.57-8.87	17.75-18.00	3.41-3.50	1-2	1003-1017	No Recommended
Pond 3	6.00-7.83	20.87-21.06	3.31-3.49	1-2	1179-1190	Recommended
Pond 4	6.51-8.30	21.06-21.44	3.60-3.62	2-4	1193-1215	Recommended
Pond 5	3.84-3.95	21.06-21.25	3.56-3.58	1-3	1190-1203	No recommended

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an automated IoT framework for real-time data monitoring is proposed and successfully instigated using diverse sensors and circuits as demonstrated in different figures. We experimented using 5 scenarios for obtaining real-time values including pH, temperature, conductivity, depth, and turbidity values. After analyzing the real-time values, pond 1, pond 3 and pond 4 are perfect in fish farming and pond 2 and pond 5 are not perfect for fish farming. That is why, end-user can cultivate fish in pond 1, pond 3, and pond 4. For pond 2 and pond 5, a farmer can take any step for utilizing these ponds for fish farming later. As the proposed model is automatically controlled, it will help the farmers to properly monitor their ponds. The implementation enables the sensor to provide data to the ThingSpeak server. The results show that the system presented is capable of assessing water quality indicators in real time, transmitting data to the Cloud, and informing users of water quality. In future, the proposed architecture may be tested with more aquatic environment parameters by targeting specific fish species.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Md. Monirul Islam has been studying as an M.Sc. in Engineering Student, Department of Computer Science and Engineering (CSE), Dhaka University of Engineering & Technology (DUET), Gazipur-1700, Bangladesh. He has completed B.Sc. in engineering degree in CSE in the year 2017 from Pabna University of Science and Technology (PUST), Pabna-6600, Bangladesh. Currently, he is at Uttara University (UU) as a full-time lecturer since 3rd February 2020. Field of interest: Machine learning/Deep learning, Data science. He can be contacted at email: monir.duet.cse@gmail.com.

Mohammad Abul Kashem has been serving as an Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering (CSE) and Additional Director, Planning & Development, Dhaka University of Engineering & Technology (DUET), Gazipur-1700, Bangladesh. He got Post Doctorate (ULL, France), PhD (LPNU, Ukraine), M.Eng. & B.Eng. (SULP, Ukraine). Field of interest: Internet of Things, Cyber Physical System, The Challenges, Approaches and Used Techniques of CPS for Manufacturing in Industry 4.0, CPS of collaborative value network for manufacturing, Multi Agent System for Industry and Critical Mission. He can be contacted at email: drkashemll@duet.ac.bd.

Jia Uddin is as an Assistant Professor, AI and Big Data Department, Endicott College, Woosong University, Daejeon, South Korea. He received Ph.D. in Computer Engineering from University of Ulsan, South Korea, M.Sc. in Electrical Engineering (Specialization: Telecommunications), Blekinge Institute of Technology, Sweden, and B.Sc. in Computer and Communication Engineering, International Islamic University Chittagong, Bangladesh. He was a visiting faculty at School of computing, Staffordshire University, United Kingdom. He is an Associate Professor (now on leave), Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Brac University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. His research interests are Industrial Fault Diagnosis, Machine Learning/Deep Learning based prediction and detection using multimedia signals. He can be contacted at email: jia.uddin@wsu.ac.kr.